

Evaluation of penetration resistance and bearing capacity of a small-diameter spiral pile by similitude model tests using seepage force

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, with application to soft ground with poor conditions in mind, the development of techniques to build foundation types using spiral piles has been progressing. However, there have been few examples of experiments conducted under strict control and conditions closer to real phenomena. Therefore, in this study, we performed a scale-similar model experiment that reproduced the stress state of the actual scale ground by loading the seepage force and clarified the vertical bearing capacity characteristics of the spiral pile in the saturated sandy ground. This paper reports the results of penetration and vertical loading experiments on the saturated ground using straight and spiral piles. The experiment results clarify the differences in the support mechanisms of the two types of piles in a full-scale saturated ground.

Keywords: pile foundation, model experiment, seepage force, vertical loading test, bearing capacity

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, with application to soft ground with poor ground conditions in mind, the development of foundation types using short steel pipe piles with small diameters, spiral piles and diagonal piles has progressed (Araki, 2013; Mohajerani, 2016; Sato, 2015; Hirata, 2005). In particular, spiral piles are used for construction on soft ground and reinforcement of slopes because the integration of the spiral pile with the surrounding ground is effectively achieved by rotary press-fitting (Hamasaki, 2018; Kasama, 2020). In previous studies, Experimental observation to determine the efficiency of the ultimate bearing capacity of screw pile configurations in lateral loading (Amarbayar, 2021) and horizontal loading tests on spiral piles and cylindrical piles to investigate the tendency of the pile group effect of the spiral pile (Ohnishi, 2021) have also been conducted. However, the design for the spiral pile foundation has been done on the safe side without considering this integration effect from the press-fitting. In addition, many past studies used dry sand for the foundation. Few studies have been done under more realistic conditions and strict control, including the use of viscous soil and

unsaturated ground under conditions where suction is controlled. Based on the above, if the actual ground conditions and bearing capacity characteristics of the spiral pile on the actual scale ground can be appropriately evaluated and the spiral pile foundation is designed more rationally, the scope of application of the spiral pile can be expected to expand further in the future. Therefore, in this study, we performed a scale-similar model experiment that reproduced the stress state in the actual scale ground by loading the seepage force on sandy ground and clarified the vertical bearing capacity characteristics of the spiral pile in the saturated ground. This paper reports the results of a penetration experiment and a vertical loading experiment on the saturated ground using straight piles and spiral piles.

2 SIMILARITY LAW

The seepage force was used instead of the centrifugal force in the centrifugal model experiment to make the stress in the model ground the same as that of the actual scale ground. The ground depths of 4.5 m and 8.6 m in the actual ground were reproduced by applying air pressures of 40 kPa and 80 kPa to the model saturated ground, respectively, considering the similarity rule in a

previous study (Kato, 2012). Assuming that the standard permeability coefficient of saturated ground is 1.0×10^{-4} m/s, the loading speeds described later for actual piles are 0.282 times and 0.287 times those for model piles by applying air pressure of 40 kPa and 80 kPa, respectively.

3 SOIL CHAMBER AND MODEL PILES

In this study, a soil chamber for applying seepage force loading was prepared with reference to a previous study (Kato et al., 2012) as shown in Fig. 1. The soil chamber was an acrylic cylindrical structure with a diameter of 300 mm and a height of 640 mm. By applying a seepage force, the stress state of the actual scale ground was reproduced in the gravity field, and various types of loading experiments on the structures in the ground, such as piles, were able to be carried out. The seepage force can be managed by changing the air pressure in the cell, while continuously measuring the pore water pressure and the amount of drainage water.

Fig. 1 Soil chamber (left: At penetration, right: At static loading).

We prepared straight piles and spiral piles with different shapes (Fig. 2 and Table 1). We created two types of straight piles (normal piles (NP))—one was 12 mm in diameter (NP12) and the other was 25 mm in diameter (NP25)—and three types of spiral piles. We defined the angle between the horizontal plane and the slope of the wing structure as the spiral angle, and created three types of spiral piles with different spiral angles: one with a spiral angle of 15 degrees (SP15), one with an angle of 30 degrees (SP30), and one with an angle of 45 degrees (SP45). These piles were created as closed-tip piles by closing the tip with a cone-shaped structure. To measure axial force, two strain gauges per cross-section were attached to the inner surface of each pile at five

locations. The locations for attaching gauges on the spiral pile were the same as those for NP12. Prior to these experiments, the cross-sectional rigidity of each pile was obtained from the axial compression test in the air, and the axial force at each location of the pile was calculated from the measured strain and the cross-sectional rigidity.

Fig. 2 Model piles.

Table 1. Data on the model piles.

	NP12	NP25	SP15	SP30	SP45
Mass (kg)	0.056	0.266	0.096	0.073	0.064
Length (mm)	313	324.7	313	313	313
Pile diameter (mm)	12	25	12	12	12
Wing diameter (mm)	-	-	25	25	25
Wing pitch (mm)	-	-	14	29	50
Young's modulus (GPa)	69.1	70.6	70.8	69.2	71.7

4 Experiment procedure

Silica sand No. 7 ($\rho_{\max} = 1.60$ g/cm³, $\rho_{\min} = 1.25$ g/cm³, $\rho_s = 2.45$ g/cm³) was used for the modeling of the saturated ground. The model ground of 360 mm in height and a relative density of $Dr = 45\%$ was prepared by the air pluviation technique. After preparing the dry sand ground, water was infiltrated from the bottom of the soil chamber to create a saturated ground.

After creating the saturated ground, a vertical seepage flow was generated by opening a drainage outlet while applying a constant air pressure (40 kPa or 80 kPa) from the air supply port. The model pile penetration was done under the above condition. The amount of pile penetration was set to 260 mm from the tip of the pile (100 mm from the bottom of the soil chamber, which was four times the maximum pile diameter) so the influence of the bottom of the soil tank was able to be ignored. The straight pile was press-fit by placing a weight on the top of the metal fixture for rotating the pile. The spiral piles were rotationally penetrated. A weight was placed on the top of the metal fixture for rotating, and the metal fixture was manually rotated in the clockwise direction, which was the winding direction of the spiral wing. When penetrating the spiral

pile, the rotation speed was manually adjusted so the penetration amount per rotation and the wing pitch of each spiral pile agreed.

After the pile was penetrated, the loading device was installed with the continuous generation of the seepage flow, and the static loading experiment was carried out. As shown in Fig. 3, three cycles of a positive (pushing) and negative (pulling) alternate loading were done at a loading speed of about 0.5 mm/min. The resistance force of the pile when the vertical displacement reached 10% of the pile diameter (wing diameter in the case of a spiral pile) was defined as the ultimate bearing capacity of the pile. Thus, the ultimate bearing capacity was considered to be reached when the vertical displacement reached 1.2 mm for NP12 and 2.5 mm for NP25 and the spiral piles.

Fig. 3. Loading method.

From the start of the pile penetration to the end of loading, the pore water pressure at five locations inside the model ground was measured with pressure gauges, and the amounts of water supply and drainage were measured with the flow meters, respectively. We verified that the measured values did not change during the experiment and concluded that the experiment was carried out under a constant seepage flow.

5. EXPERIMENT RESULTS

The pushing direction and pulling direction will be described as the positive and negative values in this section and after.

Fig. 4 shows the relationship between the penetration resistance of the pile and the displacement ratio (the ratio of the displacement amount to the target penetration amount of 260 mm) at the time of penetration with the air pressure of 40 kPa for each pile. By comparing the final penetration resistance values of the three types of spiral piles with those of NP25, which has a shaft diameter equal to the wing diameter of the three types of spiral piles, we found that the final penetration resistance of the three types of spiral piles

were significantly lower than that of NP25. Based on this, the effect of reducing the penetration resistance in the actual-scale saturated ground by the rotary penetration of spiral piles was clearly demonstrated.

Fig. 5 shows the relationship between the penetration resistance and displacement ratio of the piles at the penetration in the experiment on NP12 and SP30 with air pressure of 40 kPa and 80 kPa. It shows that the changes in the curves of NP12 and SP30 under the air pressure of 40 kPa and 80 kPa roughly exhibit a similar tendency even though the wing diameter of the SP30 is larger than the pile shaft diameter of the NP12.

Fig. 6 shows the relationship between the penetration resistance and the displacement ratio of the pile at the pile penetration on the dry sandy ground. The degrees of the penetration resistance of the three spiral piles in this figure differ from those on the similar-scale ground under saturated condition. This figure shows that the smaller the spiral angle of the spiral pile, the smaller the penetration resistance. Therefore, factors other than the decreasing effect in the penetration resistance by the rotary penetration of the spiral pile, for example, the weight of the pile and disturbance in the ground near the pile wing due to rotational penetration, are considered to have an influence on the value of penetration resistance at the deeper locations.

Fig. 7 shows the relationship between the penetration ratio (δ/p_w) and the displacement ratio. Where δ : the amount of penetration for one rotation, p_w : the length of wing pitch. The average penetration ratio ($\delta/p_{w\text{ Ave.}}$) for each pile during the entire penetration process is defined as the following equation; (the target penetration length (260 mm) - free fall displacement δ_n) / (number of rotation $n \times p_w$). In Fig. 7, the penetration ratios for three types of spiral piles show unstable and great changes at the initial penetration stage, but the values approach 1 as the rotary penetration progresses. From the average penetration ratio (δ/p_w)_{Ave.}, it is understood that the rotary penetration was done in the process in which the amount of penetration for one rotation of the spiral pile roughly agrees with the pitch of each spiral pile.

Fig. 4. Penetration resistance vs displacement ratio (40 kPa).

Fig. 5. Penetration resistance vs displacement ratio (comparison between 40 kPa and 80 kPa).

Fig. 6. Penetration resistance vs displacement ratio (dry sand).

Fig. 7. Penetration ratio vs displacement ratio.

Fig. 8. shows the relationship between the load on the pile to the normalized displacement by the respective pile diameter in the static loading with the air pressure of 40 kPa for each pile type. In Fig. 8, the rigidity of the straight pile decreases with the increase in the pushing direction displacement in the first loading cycle. In the second and third cycles of the pushing loading on NP12 and NP25, the bearing capacity became lower than that for the first cycle when the displacement ratio passed around 1% for NP12 and around 3% for NP25. The

rigidity of the spiral pile remained nearly constant during the first cycle of the pushing loading. In the second and third cycles of the pushing loading on SP15 and SP30, the bearing capacity did not become lower than that of the first cycle until the displacement ratio exceeded around 8% for SP15 and 7% for SP30. In the second and third cycles of pushing loading for SP45, the bearing capacity did not become lower than that of the first cycle until the displacement ratio had reached 10%. Based on the above, the spiral piles can be evaluated as more robust over the cyclic loading than the straight piles. In pulling loading, the pulling resistance of the spiral pile gradually increases with the increase in the displacement after the loading reached the yield point. In pulling loading on the straight pile, the displacement drastically increases with the pulling resistance being constant after the loading value reached the yield point. This difference in the resistance-displacement relationship in the two types of piles can be explained based on the fact that the spiral pile possesses a mechanism to exert skin friction, in which the skin friction of the spiral pile recovers and starts to work with the increase in the displacement. In the pulling loading, the bearing capacity in the second and third cycles were lower than that in the first cycle for all piles starting at the early loading stage. The superiority of the spiral pile, which was observed in the pushing loading, was not well observed in the pulling loading.

Fig. 9 shows the relationship between the load and the normalized displacement by the pile diameter at the static loading experiment on NP12 and SP30 with the air pressure of 40 kPa and 80 kPa. It shows that the rigidity of NP12 decreases with the increase of displacement in the first cycle of pushing loading as well as in the case of 40 kPa air pressure. In the second and third cycles of the pushing loading on NP12, the bearing capacity became lower than that for the first cycle when the displacement ratio passed around 4.5% for NP12. On the other hand, in SP30, the rigidity remained nearly constant during the first cycle of the pushing loading even in the case of 80 kPa air pressure as in the case of 40 kPa air pressure. In addition, the bearing capacity in the second and third cycles did not become lower than that of the first cycle until the displacement ratio had reached 10%. From these points, the spiral pile exhibited superiority in the two different stress conditions for pushing loading.

Fig. 10 shows the relationship between the load and the normalized displacement by the pile diameter in the case of the dry sandy ground. The rigidity of the straight pile in the first pushing loading cycle decreased with the increase in the displacement in the direction of pushing, and the rigidity of the spiral pile remained nearly constant in the same loading condition as that for the straight pile. The bearing mechanism of the straight pile and that of the spiral pile in the static loading

showed similar tendencies as those in the saturated actual-scale ground.

Fig. 8 Load vs displacement ratio (40 kPa).

Fig. 9 Load vs displacement ratio (comparison between 40 kPa and 80 kPa).

Fig. 10. Load vs displacement ratio (dry ground).

Table 2 shows the ultimate penetration resistance R (kN), the ultimate bearing capacity Q (kN) at the first cycle of static pushing loading, and the ratio of the two (Q/R) for each pile. The Q/R values for the straight piles are close to unity, that is, the Q and R are nearly equal, but the Q values are greater than the R values for

the spiral piles. In the current experiment using the similar-scale seepage force model also, we obtained similar results as those of the past study (Sato et al., 2015). It is possible to maintain low penetration resistance of the pile and achieve high bearing capacity by performing the rotary penetration in which the amount of penetration for one rotation of the spiral pile roughly agrees with the wing pitch.

Table 2 Ultimate bearing capacity Q /Penetration resistance R .

	R (kN)	Q (kN)	Q/R
40kPa			
NP12	26.34	26.83	1.02
NP25	67.54	75.24	1.11
SP15	10.51	77.03	7.33
SP30	33.01	124.19	3.76
SP45	18.76	71.42	3.81
80kPa			
NP12	106.53	94.96	0.89
SP30	94.58	272.45	2.88

Figs. 11 and 12 show the changes in the end bearing capacity (V_5) to the total vertical bearing capacity of a pile at the pushing loading (V) with the air pressure of 40 kPa and 80 kPa, respectively. The share of the end bearing capacity of the straight pile increases with the increase in the displacement. On the contrary, the share of the end bearing capacity of the spiral pile decreases with the increase in the displacement, excluding the first cycle on SP30. Based on the above findings, as described earlier, it is considered that the spiral pile exerts greater skin friction with the increase in the displacement.

Fig. 11 Share of the point bearing capacity (40 kPa).

Fig. 12 Share of the point bearing capacity (80 kPa).

6 CONCLUSIONS

I. The penetration resistance of the spiral pile on the actual scale saturated ground can be kept low by performing the rotary penetration in which the amount of penetration agrees with the wing pitch of the pile.

II. Spiral piles are more useful compared with straight piles because of their small decreasing effect in the ultimate bearing capacity in the repeated loading on the actual scale saturated ground.

III. A loading-settlement relationship similar to that under the seepage force of 40 kPa was observed under that of 80 kPa. The superiority of the spiral pile in pushing loading was observed even with the changes in the scale.

IV. The difference in the bearing mechanism between the straight pile and spiral pile in the actual scale saturated ground can be explained based on the difference in the displacement level in which the skin friction is fully exerted. The spiral pile has a mechanism whereby it exerts the maximum skin friction with the increase in the displacement.

V. In the spiral pile, it is possible to maintain low penetration resistance of the pile and achieve high bearing capacity by performing the rotary penetration in which the amount of penetration for one rotation of the pile roughly agrees with the wing pitch.

7 FUTURE ISSUES

In this study, we elucidated the usefulness of the spiral piles, which was observed in the increased wing resistance effect and endurance in repeated loading in the experiment using the seepage force on the similar-scale model ground. We are planning to clarify the reproducibility of the result of the experiment in this study by performing reproduction analyses using the FEM. We are also planning to conduct similar experiments with samples other than silica sand No. 7 used in this study (silt, clay, peat, etc.).

The future study plan includes clarification of the

bearing characteristics of the spiral pile in the unsaturated ground by creating an unsaturated ground by using a continuous pressure experiment technique and the seepage force loading device used in the experiment in this study.

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REFERENCES

- 1) Amarbayar, J., Yasufuku, N., Tani, Y., Kurokawa, T. and Nagata, M. (2021): Experimental observation on the ultimate lateral capacity of vertical-batter screw pile under monotonic loading in cohesionless soil, Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Press-in Engineering 2021, Kochi, Japan, 210-217.
- 2) Araki, K. (2013): Simplified Foundation Method Subject to Small-scale Structures "PIN FOUNDATION METHOD," Geotechnical engineering magazine, 61(8), 32-33 (in Japanese).
- 3) Hamasaki, T., Kasama, K., Tayama, S., Maeda, Y., Matsukaya, K. and Akiyoshi, R. (2018): Field test for embankment reinforcement using spiral bladed drain pipes, Journal of Japan Society of Civil Engineers, Ser. C (Geosphere Engineering), 74(1), 20-33 (in Japanese).
- 4) Hirata, A., Kokaji, S., Seung, K. S. and Goto, T. (2005): Study on the Estimation of the Axial Resistance of Spiral Bar Based on Interaction with Ground, Shigen-to-Sozai, 121(8), 370-377 (in Japanese).
- 5) Kasama, K., Hamasaki, T., Ito, Y., Furukawa, Z. and Matsukata K. (2020): Stability evaluation of highway embankment reinforced with spiral bladed drain pipe reinforcements, Journal of Japan Society of Civil Engineers, Ser. C (Geosphere Engineering), 76(1), 99-109 (in Japanese).
- 6) Kato, T. and Kokusho, T. (2012): RATE-DEPENDENT PULL-OUT BEARING CAPACITY OF PILES BY SIMILITUDE MODEL TESTS USING SEEPAGE FORCE, Journal of Japan Society of Civil Engineers, Ser. C (Geosphere Engineering), 68(1), 117-126 (in Japanese).
- 7) Mohajerani, A., Bosnjak, D. and Bromwich, D. (2016): Analysis and design methods of screw piles: A review, Soils and Foundations, 56(1), 115-128.
- 8) Ohnishi, N. and Nishioka, H. (2021): Experimental study on the pile group effect in the horizontal resistance of spiral piles, Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Press-in Engineering 2021, Kochi, Japan, 203-209.
- 9) Sato, T., Harada, T., Iwasa, N., Hayashi, S. and Otani, J. (2015): Effect of shaft rotation of spiral piles under its installation on vertical bearing capacity, Japanese Geotechnical Journal, 10(2), 253-265 (in Japanese).